
BUILD UP SCHOOL CULTURE THROUGH IMPLEMENTATION OF CHARACTER EDUCATION

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Abstract:

In a Globalization era, school has to build up a positive culture to prepare Millennial Generation in science, technology and character. The passion of the founders in the school's vision and mission became the basic for building up the school culture. Every year, there must be a changing of school components, a graduating class, a freshman who will take a new class, and also the teachers and staff. That conditions make them can't work in a same passion and achieve school's goals. Building up the school culture means to build up habits in applying school's values (religiosity, nationalism, independence, mutual cooperation, and integrity), carrying out school rules, having work's habits to achieve the goals of the school. Character education in curriculum 2013, provides a space for school to build up the school culture through the habituation of character education and being a role model. Starting with respect, curiosity, perseverance and courage school culture can be stronger than the previous year and the all school components can bring good influences in the school.

Keywords: Education; School Culture; Character Education; Habituation.

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1. Introduction

School culture that was built from the beginning of the school stood – good things accompanied the development process of the school. In line with Zamroni [1] which states that in school culture there are forms of values, principles, traditions and customary habits that are formed in the long journey of the school, developed by the school for long periods of time and become the hint and belief of all school members to encourage the emergence of attitudes and behavior of school residents. Gibson et al [2] state that organizational culture as such, Organization culture involves shared expectations, values, and attitude. It influences on individuals, groups, and organizational processes. For example, if quality is important in the culture, then individuals are expected to adopt this behavior. The other hand is set to a specific set of dealing with customers is norm, then this type of behavior would be expected, recognized, and rewarded. Mullin [3] explained that the Organization culture of the collection of traditions, values, policies, beliefs, and attitudes that constitute a pervasive context for everything we do and think in organizations. The culture of an organization is also often linked to the personality of individuals

Based on the observations, researcher found an interesting case to be researched and developed. Elim Baptist Junior High School is located in Region Grogol-Petamburan which is a densely populated area. It becomes interesting because this Christian school can work together, side by side well with other schools. Organization culture by Robbins et al [4] is the social glue that helps hold the organization together by providing standards for what employees should say and do. Finally, it is a sense-making and control mechanism that guides and shapes employees attitude and behaviour. The right culture will bring positive influence to the surrounding environment. Being in the midst of plurality, did not make the spirit to promote this education is reduced. Value of character which is built already can make the middle school characteristic in the middle Grogol's environment.

As a Christian school, which has built since 1986 is certainly a school culture that teaches Christian character and high sense of nationalism remains upholding escorting school development. Character Education be applied through the lessons and daily practice in schools. Character Education by Albertus [5] is the place given to individual liberty in living up to values are regarded as good, noble, and worth fighting as a guideline to behave for dealing with his personal life, others and God. Character education is a process of activities carried out with all the power and conscious and planned effort to steer students. Khan [6] states that character education is also an activity process that leads to improving the quality of education and the development of harmony of mind that always teaches, guides, and fosters every human being to have intellectual competence, character, and interesting skills.

On its way to escalate quality of schools, the construction of school culture needs to be considered. School conditions should follow the development of the era make Elim Baptist SMP should also continue to enrich themselves with the changing times that happened. Character education in the curriculum in 2013 that includes also take on the role of cultural development of the school. Key to the success of building and developing the school culture is the existence of ties between the school community were awakened. Darayanto [7] states that the relationship that is built will cause the values accepted and internalized by the school community. Character education is one of the government's main concern in order to prepare his nation mental revolution in the 2045 golden generation later. The programs that have been carried out apparently formed a habit that affect school culture. Hopefully, by the instructions of the government, the values and character of this nation could increasingly shape the culture of the school is getting better. In its application need to get used to Elim Baptist junior record and document the activities that have been done. This research is expected to see significant way of development of the school culture through the implementation of character education.

Lewis [8] explained that the school culture is beliefs and attitudes that affect every aspect of how the school functions. Culture shared by all school stakeholders make short-term and long-actualization, In school, we develop education based on the local culture charge. Murtako [9] explained that education can not be separated from culture. It is a product of human culture and become a part of the culture. It also seeks to change the value of its culture to reach individuals and communities forward. Implementation of culture-based character education highlights the importance of exemplary elements.

Research in Turkey conducted by Gundogdu et al. [10] states that character education in the last ten years has become the research trend of academics. That makes researchers there to probe further the development of character education at various age levels. In another study Syamsu [11] stated that character education programs have been carried out both formally and informally by referring to the vision and mission of the institutions concerned. The goals that are well prepared will help guide education that is also good in its application. Dodds [12] examined the influence of character education as well as the process and results of student academic achievement. This reveals the importance of character education instilled early in the educational environment. Based on previous research, this further strengthens researchers to be more serious in examining school culture which is influenced by character education. In Indonesia, this is very relevant and very real. In a very fast development, a superior school culture will help students become more comfortable living a community life. Not only cognitive intelligence but their ability to socialize, interact with the environment, education of religious, nationalist, mutual cooperation, independence, integrity is needed to frame it all.

2. Materials and Methods

The approach used in this study is a qualitative approach, qualitative research, research that does not use a calculation or termed scientific research that emphasizes the natural character of the data source. Meanwhile, according Sukmadinata qualitative study [13] of a study aimed to describe and analyze the phenomena, events, social activities, attitudes, beliefs, perceptions, thoughts of people individually or in groups. In this research, the researcher took the case about how the implementation of character education to build a culture of Elim Baptist junior high school.

The case study by Yin [14] is an empirical inquiry investigating the phenomenon in the context of real life, whenever; the boundaries between phenomenon and context do not seem firmly and where: multiple sources of evidence used. As a case study inquiry should not be done in a long time and do not also have to depend on the data ethnography or participant observation. In fact, according to a researcher Yin could have a valid case studies and high quality without leaving the library, depending on the topics to be investigated.

Researcher collected data by interviewing, observation and documentation. Interviews were conducted with school principals and then advised to go to the vice principal, teachers, staff and students. The data obtained and processed further, ie from data reduction, data presentation and conclusion. Data reduction is a form of data analysis are sharpened, wish important things, classifies direct, dispose of unneeded and organize data in order to systematically and can make a meaningful conclusion. Thus, the data obtained through observation, interviews, review of documents collected, selected and grouped then concluded by not eliminate the value of the data itself. Presentation of data is a compilation set of information that gives the possibility of drawing conclusions in the decision-tindakan. The conclusion is only temporary and the public. To the conclusion that "grounded" it is necessary to find new other data for testing conclusions.

3. Results and Discussions

Based on observations and interviews conducted, to get the intact results, researcher conducted the interviews with three different sources. It was found that the school culture in Elim Baptist Middle

School was a unity. School culture that is seen is a tangible manifestation of characters and other values that make this culture stronger. Character education is measured by the character values to be applied, namely: (1) religious; (2) nationalists; (3) mutual cooperation; (4) independent; (5) integrity. Suhadisiwi [15] stated that the five values are expected to be a reference for every education unit in Indonesia to develop Character Education Emphasis for Indonesia's golden generation.

In carrying out each of its activities every educational institution, as each individual in an educational institution is different from each other. Each has a characteristic that becomes a strength in achieving its goals. Beare et al. [16] explained that like humans, a school has its own vibration and soul. Each of them expresses his own important taste that is different from each other. These vibrations come from the school environment which in turn creates a culture of an educational institution. Holistic support from all aspects can build a school culture.

3.1. Result

3.1.1. Religious Character

Religious character is one of the characters that is the focus of research. This character becomes very basic because the other characters will wake up strongly if the foundation is strong. The school principal provides information about religious characters that are accustomed to morning worship in class before starting the lesson. There is weekly worship with all students. The thing to pay attention to is that the student's task schedule needs to be controlled so that everything goes in an orderly manner. As educators, we also continue to assist each preparation, because even though we have been given the trust to regulate the way of worship, we still need periodic assistance. These things must be accustomed to better habituation and regularity. Mulyana et al. [17] argue that habituation methods need to be applied by the teacher in the process of character formation, to familiarize students with commendable and good traits, so that the activities carried out by students are positively recorded. A teacher revealed that he tried to live out what I was teaching. Teachers every day, before starting the lesson start with reflection in each class. The teacher also invites students to actively participate in working on their parts. There is a schedule for who is the morning reflection leader.

One student gives answers to religious characters. The application of religious character that I experience is when every day not only get Christian religious teaching, but I get behavior that describes it. This helped me and my friends grow more Christian character. Devotional Activities Morning, weekly worship, Christmas and Easter events are all a series of activities that can support religious character.

3.1.2. Nationalists Character

The application of nationalist characters can be seen when scout activities, flag ceremonies, and movements love Indonesian culture. The principal and the teacher providing information for this character is to get used to having a prepared attitude in carrying out the flag ceremony, scouts. Evaluation for this character is in preparation for the ceremony, students must be more serious in carrying out each task given. The nationalist sense of children still needs to be added so that they

continue to get used to respecting the culture of this nation. Habit is the cultivation of doing and saying skills. This is consistent with that of Fadillah et al. [18] stating that habituation in essence has more profound implications than the planting of ways of acting and pronunciation.

The students interviewed about nationalist characters giving information the real thing we did was to actively participate in ceremonies on Monday and other national holidays. We also often post nationalist messages on school wall magazines. Students, teachers, principals, TU and all school employees are involved. Activities that can support nationalist character are flag ceremonies, representing schools for competitions, loving local products, and scouts. His suggestion to increase nationalism is to collaborate with elementary and kindergarten levels to make cultural and artistic performances.

3.1.3. Character of Mutual Cooperation

The spirit of mutual cooperation is one of the national identities of Indonesia. People who are friendly and like to work together are not individualistic as this nation's style. Along with the development of the times, the spirit was increasingly eroded. The principal and the teacher provide answers about building the character of mutual cooperation in school. The simple implementation of the mutual cooperation character in preparing the ceremony, the student council activities, students were emphasized to work together. The teachers also gave examples of mutual cooperation. Collaboration between teachers and students can also be seen in preparing for the Introduction to the School Environment, Students, teachers and principals. In the spirit of mutual cooperation at school, there is still comparing workloads so that they are not sincere in cooperating together, this makes the mutual cooperation difficult. By working together, the character of students and other school residents continues to be honed. Muslih [19] remembers that character education aims to improve the quality of implementation and educational outcomes that lead to the achievement of the formation of character and noble character of students as a whole, integrated and balanced. The balance of students here is seen from their ability to use all their knowledge to jointly work together to realize the ideals of the nation.

As students, they also feel that they have jointly implemented a mutual cooperation spirit. Mutual cooperation activities can be implemented in daily activities, together with lifting trash cans, class pickets. Constraints in mutual cooperation there is still a sense of laziness in working on common tasks. Evaluation of mutual cooperation which is a spirit of togetherness must continue to be nurtured so that it is not easily shaken.

3.1.4. Independent Character

Being part of an independent community, making the dynamics in the community more alive. A person will become more confident, trustworthy and have good analytical skills. The principal gives information about independence. The application of independent characters is to give space for students to explore their own knowledge and skills after getting the teacher's explanation. All school citizens provide examples of independence in carrying out their duties. Chaplin [20] explains that independence is a condition where a person is not dependent on others in determining decisions and the attitude of self-confidence. The teacher gave a response about the character of this independence. The teacher provides space for students to explore independence in

understanding a material. Independence starts from oneself, they are accustomed to solving their own problems, the teacher facilitates each learning so that students are provoked by reason. Students provide answers regarding the independent character development. How to apply this independent character through doing tasks by exploring it yourself. Students, teachers, principals, staff and all school employees also carry out independence in working to solve a problem. The activity of seeking deeper information on a problem can train students' independence. But all of that needs to be monitored by the teacher so that every search is directed. I have tried to be independent, even though it still sometimes depends on friends and teachers. Hopefully the more days I become more independent and dare to make decisions. In learning, independence seeking resources is very dependent on the internet.

3.1.5. Integrity Character

Integrity is a combination of values, words and actions. Cloud [21] explains that this integrity speaks more complex things. Integrity is closely related to the integrity and effectiveness of a person as a person. In an organization, integrity is needed so that the organization runs well and produces the desired value. The principal gives information that integrity tries by starting from yourself. To live out everything we say. From there students will imitate and want to build their integrity. Say no to bad things. Students, teachers, principals, staff and all school employees have tried to implement good integrity.

The teacher provides information about the character of integrity that the teacher in the class is the center of attention, so I make sure what I say is what I do. With me consistent with my rules, students can see that integrity. Intra and extra-curricular activities can hone their integrity character. Even in school events, integrity is needed, so that the program runs well. I personally have carried out integrity in every day's actions. The obstacle is the feeling of laziness or urgency that makes me deny what I should have done. Integrity needs to be honed early, so that it becomes more cultured and becomes good in daily life.

The students interviewed also gave responses regarding the character of this integrity. As a student, I learned a lot about integrity here, I applied it in daily life with friends. Integrity can be honed precisely in a shared community, so that the closer I am to friends, the more my integrity will be honed.

3.2. Discussion

School culture is a belief and attitude that affects every aspect of how the school functions. Lewis et al. [8] stated that the culture held by all school stakeholders made short and long-term actualization. In line with the revelation, it can be seen that the culture built in Elim Baptist Middle School is a form of short-term actualization and not long. In one year the cultural lessons built can be used as a benchmark, or an evaluation of the culture that will be set in the coming year. Religious is one of the characters that was built as the foundation of the culture of this school. Culture of love and forgiveness, respect is reflected in it. Character Education according to Albertus [5] is giving a place for individual freedom in living values that are considered good, noble, and worth fighting for as guidelines for behaving in a personal life that is confronted with him, others and

God. When students can be invited to hone their characters, it is hoped that something noble can build their lives later.

Built integrity is expected to be a long-term achievement in the running of education at Elim Baptist Middle School. According to Murtako [9] the culture of this school cannot be separated from a communion. It also seeks to change cultural values to reach advanced individuals and communities. The implementation of culture-based character education highlights the importance of exemplary elements. A growing community is a community that builds on each other in its growth. Planting character education is not done alone, but requires holistic collaboration by all school members. The real form of school participation is giving an example of the five karkater who want to be formed in Elim Baptist Middle School, the character of mutual cooperation for example, not only the teacher, or the students only. Exemplary is needed so that all of them can become agents of change and inspire others.

Gunawan [22] argues that character education is essentially aimed at forming a strong, competitive, noble, moral, tolerant, collaborative, patriotic, dynamic developing, oriented to science and technology which are all imbued with faith and piety to God Yang Supreme One based on Pancasila. It is hoped that there can be a change in the mindset that is sustainable in every school citizen.

Research in Turkey, Gundogdu [10] states that character education in the last ten years has become a research trend for academics. That makes researchers there to probe further the development of character education at various age levels. In schools, there are various levels of age, which are all individuals who are still and continue to learn from time to time. Implementation This character education makes all school members become part of the learning. As an example of how the character of Integrity can be done with self-involvement alone. Or the character of mutual cooperation which also requires other people to continue to hone their character. So that it is in accordance with the journal above which explains that character education is a trend developed in various levels of age.

According to Zamroni [1] it is limiting that school culture is a pattern of values, principles, traditions and habits that are formed in the long journey of the school, developed by the school for a long period of time and become the guideline and belief of all school people so that encourage the emergence of attitudes and behavior of school residents.

In another study Syamsu [11] stated that character education programs have been carried out both formally and informally by referring to the vision and mission of the institutions concerned. At Elim Baptist Middle School Vision Mission reflects the five characters that are cool to achieve. The implementation of curriculum education is carried out based on the values of the foundation that have been crystallized in the vision and mission. Religious, nationalist, mutual cooperation, independence, integrity are reflected in the implementation of school activities. The school activities are prepared and designed based on the school's vision and mission. Because there are no activities designed not to realize the School's Vision and Mission to be real and clear.

Dodds [12] in his research explained that character education also influences the process and results of student academic achievement. This reveals the importance of character education

instilled early in the educational environment. The educational environment is very appropriate as a location to implement character education in addition to family and society. From an early age, character education was indeed instilled so that more years of honing and producing fruit every year of the student's life. For example nationalist characters are taught from an early age so that in the future, he will not forget the identity of his people and be a good example in representing Indonesia later.

The research if visualized can be described as follows.

Figure 1: School Culture in Elim Baptist Middle School

The school culture is likened to a house building, where religious characters form the basis of this building. The religious character practiced in Elim Baptist Middle School has become a strong foundation for every school citizen, not only teachers, students also feel the impact of habituation in religious characters. This character formation affects other characters. Nationalist character, mutual cooperation, independent becomes able to stand firm in a strong foundation. So it is important that the laying of the foundation is also a serious concern. Without good morals, a person cannot be a person who has an impact on his environment. For example, many of us know a lot among smart people, using their knowledge to destroy nature, if they feel grateful for God's creation, they can certainly appreciate it well. Indonesia is a pluralistic country, supported by many religious teachings that make Indonesia stronger. Nationalist character will be built well along with independence and mutual cooperation that continue to be honed. The spirit of mutual cooperation is the hallmark of the Indonesian people; this culture is maintained so that an independent generation can meet Indonesia in 2045 gold.

This building cannot stand firmly without the things that unite it, namely respect, curiosity, courage and perseverance. School culture will be strong as well as things are developed with these characters. In diversity in Indonesia, respecting ethnic, racial, religious and class differences will make this nation even stronger. Curiosity towards local wisdom continues to be taught and brought closer to each student's life so that they become part of this nation that respects ancestral heritage.

Courage and perseverance are also needed so that the characters are realized properly. Over time the culture carried out will be internalized into a habit that affects their lives.

The highlight of this building is Integrity. Integrity characters overshadow other characters. without integrity, every other character becomes meaningless. The culture created by this school turns out to uphold integrity, what is said and taught is what is done. From the beginning students were introduced to truly understand what the meaning of integrity is so that they can run other characters well. Noble character without integrity will be in vain. In mutual cooperation we need to have a spirit of friendship and run it with good integrity. Integrity is also carried out with courage and perseverance, students are taught to dare to declare the truth in the midst of society, dare to make decisions wisely.

The analogy of school culture like this building can explain the pattern developed in this school. Every year this construction pattern is built to become a good habit in the school environment. A strong religious foundation is the foundation, pillars of nationalism, encouraging the community and independent support and integrity that overshadow it. The five components are interrelated. In order to better implement respect, curiosity, perseverance and courage to accompany building the culture of this school.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1. Conclusions

The development of the school culture in question is building habits in applying school values (religiosity, nationalist, independent, mutual cooperation, integrity). In the implementation of Elim Baptist Middle School also developed a sense of respect, curiosity, perseverance and courage in applying karate values. that is. From these characters, school culture is built and becomes a good habit in the school environment. In Middle School Baptist Elim built a school culture starting with oneself and applied all components of the school. Principals, Teachers, Students, Personnel, parents take their respective roles in building school culture. Each component unites to realize the school culture in order to achieve school goals. Character education in the 2013 curriculum provides space for schools to build school culture through refraction of character education and role models. Starting with mutual respect, responsibility and maintaining integrity, the school culture can be built stronger than the previous year and all components in the school become good influencers at school.

Character education according to Khan [6] is an activity process that leads to improving the quality of education and the development of harmony of mind that always teaches, guides, and fosters every human being to have intellectual competence, character, and interesting skills. Guiding and fostering the character of each school member is not an instant process, but with exemplary and habituation it will slowly be internalized. The practice of practicing five characters in Elim Baptist Middle School has a positive impact on the running of the school. Religious, nationalist, mutual cooperation, independence, integrity give color to each of the things done in school as a whole. This habituation starts from yourself and keeps trying to get the closest people together to carry out the desired character together.

4.2. Recommendation

Habitualization of character education is carried out not only in the classroom but in the school environment, so that it is clear that school is a unity in educating and educating the nation's children. This is very good to do so that every year the School has an improvement or improvement from the school culture, so that rotation in the school community does not become a barrier.

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